

Exploratory analysis of marine electrification potentials of vessels in the Spanish sea

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i. Resum

L'electrificació dels vaixells de passatgers és vital per aconseguir una societat de baixes emissions de carboni i reduir les emissions de gasos d'efecte hivernacle en el sector del transport. Aquest article presenta un estudi centrat en el potencial de substituir els vaixells de passatgers dependents de combustibles fòssils a Espanya amb motors de propulsió elèctrica. Per avaluar la fiabilitat d'aquesta transició, s'han tingut en compte diferents indicadors, desenvolupant representacions gràfiques i recursos d'informació sintetitzada per relacionar els factors que fan que cada àrea o trajecte sigui digne d'electrificació i per tal d'establir un ordre de prioritat.

Els resultats indiquen que els trajectes més importants per electrificar es troben dins de la demarcació marina Levantina-Balear (LEBA). Un exemple és Ibiza-Formentera, present a les Illes Balears, amb altes taxes en gairebé tots els paràmetres i on ja s'han realitzat els primers esforços d'electrificació. Un altre exemple és València, que, tot i que al principi de l'estudi no es va tenir massa en compte, ha resultat tenir trajectes amb altes taxes en els paràmetres socioecològics i és la segona comunitat autònoma amb més dispositius d'electrificació. També s'ha observat que una altra àrea de prioritat elevada és Gibraltar-Andalusia, amb freqüències de fins a 13,662 trajectes a l'any i un índex socioecològic (SEIx) que arriba a valors de 2.67, que, tot i no ser els més alts, superen la mitjana. En aquesta última comunitat autònoma, els esforços d'electrificació també semblen haver estat notables (11 dispositius). En termes de demarcacions, però, no sembla que es vegi tan reflectit, ja que es divideix entre la demarcació marina Sud-atlàntica (SUD) i la demarcació de l'Estret i Alborán (ESAL).

Aquest estudi contribueix als esforços en curs per electrificar els vaixells de passatgers a Espanya i reduir les emissions de gasos d'efecte hivernacle. Identifica les trajectòries de vaixells més prometedores per al model de propulsió elèctrica amb bateries en el transport local, posant èmfasi en la necessitat d'optimitzar les rutes i realitzar estudis de viabilitat detallats. Mitjançant l'electrificació dels vaixells de passatgers, Espanya pot jugar un paper important en l'avenç cap a un sistema de transport sostenible i descarbonitzat, alhora que ofereix opcions de transport marítim eficients i respectuoses amb el medi ambient per als seus passatgers.

ii. Resumen

La electrificación de los barcos de pasajeros es vital para lograr una sociedad de bajas emisiones de carbono y reducir las emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero en el sector del transporte. Este artículo presenta un estudio centrado en el potencial de reemplazar los

buques de pasajeros dependientes de combustibles fósiles en España con motores de propulsión eléctrica.

Para evaluar la confiabilidad de esta transición, se han tenido en cuenta diferentes indicadores, desarrollando representaciones gráficas y recursos de información sintetizada para relacionar los factores que hacen que cada área o viaje valga la pena ser electrificado y para establecer un orden de prioridad.

Los resultados indican que los viajes más importantes para electrificar se encuentran dentro de la demarcación marina Levantino-Balear (LEBA). Un ejemplo es Ibiza-Formentera, presente en las Islas Baleares, con altas tasas en casi todos los parámetros y donde ya se han realizado los primeros esfuerzos de electrificación. Otro ejemplo es Valencia, que al principio del estudio no fue considerada en gran medida, pero resultó tener viajes con altas tasas en los parámetros socio ecológicos y es la segunda comunidad autónoma que presenta más dispositivos de electrificación. También se ha observado que otra área de alta prioridad es Gibraltar-Andalucía, con frecuencias de hasta 13,662 viajes al año y un índice socio ecológico (SEIx) que alcanza valores de 2.67 que, aunque no son los más altos, están por encima del promedio. En esta última comunidad autónoma, los esfuerzos de electrificación también parecen haber sido contundentes (11 dispositivos), pero en términos de demarcaciones POEM, no parece estar tan reflejado, ya que se divide en la demarcación marina Sud atlántica (SUD) y la demarcación marina del Estrecho y Alborán (ESAL).

Este estudio contribuye a los esfuerzos en curso para electrificar los barcos de pasajeros en España y reducir las emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero. Identifica las trayectorias de embarcaciones más prometedoras para el transporte local en el modelo de propulsión eléctrica con baterías, enfatizando la necesidad de optimización de rutas y estudios detallados de viabilidad. Al electrificar los transbordadores de pasajeros, España puede desempeñar un papel significativo en la consecución de un sistema de transporte sostenible y descarbonizado, al tiempo que ofrece opciones de transporte marítimo eficientes y respetuosas con el medio ambiente para sus pasajeros.

iii. Abstract

The electrification of passenger ferries is vital for achieving a low carbon society and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the transportation sector. This project presents a study focused on the potential of replacing fossil fuel dependent passenger vessels in Spain with battery electric propulsion.

To assess the reliability of this transition, a review of existing scientific knowledge, national and international sustainable transition policies/strategies and geospatial and statistical

indicators have been considered, developing maps and graphic representations and adding synthesized information resources in order to characterize each sea area or ferry trajectory suitable to electrify. These efforts aim to establish an order of prioritization.

The results indicate that, the most important trips that have the potential to electrify, are inside the Levantine-Balearic marine demarcation (LEBA). An example is Ibiza-Formentera trajectory (Balearic Islands), with high rates in almost all the parameters and which is one of the first existing examples in the Spain of vessel electrification. Another example is Valencia, which at the beginning of the study was not taken into much consideration, but it has turned to have trips with high rates on socio-ecological parameters and to be the second Coastal Autonomous Community that presents more recharging devices for vessels. A review of human and ecological effects of electrified vessels shows that electrified vessels can reduce underwater noise stress and reduces risk of leakage of hazardous substances. And It has also been noticed that another high-priority area is Gibraltar-Andalusia, with frequencies up to 13,662 trips/year and Socio-ecological index (SEIx) that reach values of 2.67 that, although they are not the highest, they are above the average.

In this last Area, the electrification efforts also appear to have been forceful (11 devices), but, in terms of POEM demarcations, It does not look so reflected because it is divided in SUD and ESAL.

This study contributes to the ongoing investigations towards electrifying passenger ferries in Spain and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. It identifies the most suitable vessels trajectories of local transport for the battery electric propulsion model, emphasizing the need for route optimization and detailed feasibility studies. By electrifying passenger ferries, Spain can play a significant role in achieving a sustainable and decarbonized transportation system while providing efficient and environmentally friendly maritime transport options for its passengers.

iv. Reflection on ethics, sustainability, and gender perspective

Reflection on sustainability

Spain, as a country with significant maritime activity, has shown interest in this transition and has started various initiatives to promote the development of such technologies throughout the territory.

To provide long-term economic benefits, this electrification also presents environmental improvements compared to the current dominant system:

Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, improvement of air quality, reduction of noise and less impact on marine life.

In conclusion, there is no debate about whether the electrification of ships is ethical or not, as apart from requiring adaptation from the sector, it does not present any economic or ecological disadvantages. What could be discussed is if all countries have the resources to carry it out, but the countries that pollute the most with the transport industry are precisely those with more capital (*Npanmontojo, 2020*).

Reflection on gender perspective

In the field of environmental policies, recent OECD Survey studies on gender environment-related policies show that gender aspects are poorly integrated in terms of climate change, energy, green jobs or forestry and agriculture (*OECD, 2021*). Also, researcher women tend to have less paid jobs and they lower representation in high-profile journals (*UN, 2023*).

Another important aspect is related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 5), which has the objective to end all forms of discrimination, violence, and harmful practices against women. It also calls for their leadership at all levels of decision-making (*EU, 2023*). According to *EuroStat Report (2023)* education is of fundamental importance for social change and a condition for the achievement of essential human rights. It promotes finding quality jobs, social inclusion, and independence from violent homes. In terms of employment, the EuroStat report shows that in Europe, women are still less likely to be employed than men. The aim is to half this by 2030.

I believe that equality has already begun to be actively sought, but that there is still much to do.

1. Introduction

The electrification of ferries has gained significant attention as a promising solution for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable transportation in Spain (*La Información, 2023*). Some Spanish ferry operators have started introducing improved ferries that don't need fossil fuels to navigate into their fleets. For example, the Baleària Group, one of the leading ferry operators in Spain, operate with Natural Gas propelled ferries in the Balearic Islands. In addition, this company has already deployed their first 0 emission electric ferry which will do the route of Ibiza-Formentera (*Baleària, 2023*).

As the opposite of what it could be thought, full-electric vessels are cost competitive even under the assumed first-of-a-kind costs (first item or generation of items using a new

technology or design can cost significantly more than later items or generations), and despite the fact that the electrification objectives must be accomplished on national (Council of the European Union, 2021) and international level (*PLAN NACIONAL INTEGRADO DE ENERGÍA Y CLIMA 2021-2030, 2020*), one of the first efforts must be done on short distance trips, because, the exhaust gases of combustion affects more negatively the local population than long-distance ships do (Perčić et al., 2021) and, in addition, because on electric ferries, the range of the electric ocean-going vehicles is limited to their charge (Kersey et al., 2022). At the current stage, it must be pointed that, with the current technology limitations, the only way to make ships do a long-distance journey is by building offshore charging stations (Yang et al., 2022). The construction of these infrastructures represents a gigantic initial investment and must be accompanied by an improvement of the already existing technologies. That goal can't be achieved only by the governments, it must be done with a high contribution of some large multinationals, for which they must be given a lot of facilities that require the destination of many resources (*Electrification: the path to green ports, 2023*).

The electrification process has already advanced considerably in some countries of the EU, like, for example, in Denmark or Norway, but there are provisions to continue increasing year by year (Council of the European Union, 2021). In the end, the usage of greener fuels on maritime transportation not only has a positive impact in terms of public health (Meng and Comer, 2023), recent studies show that electrified vessels benefit the marine ecosystems by reducing the underwater noise (Parsons et al., 2020) and the shedding of hazardous substances (Hemez et al., 2020).

In this project, the overall aim is to perform a geospatial analysis of feasible ferry trajectories for electrification in the Spanish sea space, based on a database of technical, social and environmental/ecological variables. Then, a review of policy frameworks and their targets for electrified in the transportation sector is carried out and finally, an analysis based on the current scientific knowledge on socio-ecological impacts of ferry vessels in the marine environment is performed. The relation between distance and frequency, the electrification efforts that has already taken place and the impacts on the population and environment of the studied trips are also assessed to establish an order of prioritization.

2. Objectives

The main objectives of this project are:

1. Review of existing literature on electrification of ferry vessels in Spain and around the European Union
2. Analysis of existing cases of vessel electrification in Europe and definition of data for the analysis of potentials
3. Geospatial analysis to locate ferry trajectories that have the potential to be electrified in the Spanish sea space, according to the POEM demarcations and coastal regions.
4. Review of policy targets of national and international level and identify ferry trajectories that conversion could be prioritized to achieve these policy targets.
5. Review of the cost and benefit to humans and the marine environment from electrified vessel transport and development of a socio-ecological index for the prioritization of ferry vessel trajectories would reduce human and ecological impacts.

3. Methodology

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework includes the following six steps (*Figure 1*): 1) Overview of existing examples of vessel electrification and review of studies analyzing potentials; 2) Delimitation and division of the study area; 3) Data collection in order to determine the indicators required for the analysis, this included: 3.1) A review of environmental and social benefits and costs of vessel electrification 3.2) A look at the National/European policies relevant to the area of study, and 3.3) The determination and elaboration of the indicators 3.3.1) Including a survey made to the ferry operators to cover the lack of information ; 4) Data analysis; 5) Discussion of the results coming from the data analysis; 6) Conclusion of the information led in the discussion

Figure 1. Scheme of the method and steps used in the conceptual framework.

3.1 Overview of existing examples and studies

In 2019, Denmark, put in operation a boat capable of carrying 30 vehicles and 200 passengers, doing a journey of 22,5 km and being able to do it round trip between charges (*Tidey, 2019*). Also in Spain, the first electric ferry for passengers and cargo was developed this same year, 2023 by a company named Balearia. This boat operates the trip of Ibiza-Formentera, that has a length of 21,08 km and is one of the most frequented of all the Iberic Peninsula (*Figure 2; Balearia, 2023*). Having these two examples in mind, it's not rare to think that there's a limit, at least with the actual technology, on the distance that electric ships can operate, being able to finish optimally without having to worry about the lack of battery. Nowadays, the longest voyage on a single charge is made by a Danish ferry, with a distance of 90 km (*Danish Electric Ferry Completes World-record 90 km Voyage on a Single Charge, 2022*). According to a study made by the consultancy Monitor Deloitte, in maritime transport there is possibility of electrifying those routes with a fixed length between two ports with less than 100 km away (*Monitor Deloitte, 2020*). Therefore, the actual technological feasibility for electrification of the vessels considered in this study is, approximately 102 km to encompass also some ferry trips of the Canary Islands, that theoretically would be outside the range, but they have possible electrification potential according to the current level technology.

Figure 2. Cap de Barbaria vessel and the trip trajectory. Source: <https://www.balearia.com/en/cap-de-barbaria-ferry-electric>

3.2 Study area

The study area (*Figure 3*) is the territory of Spain, including the Iberic Peninsula, the Balearic Islands, the Canary Islands, Ceuta and Melilla. For the statistical analysis, it was divided into two segments:

The first segment (*Figure 3, Left*) was divided into coastal Autonomic Communities (*datos.gob.es, 2019*), namely Galicia, Asturias, Cantabria, Basque Country, Catalonia,

Valencia, Balearic Islands, Murcia, Andalusia, Ceuta, Melilla, and Canary Islands. Based on this terrestrial distinction, important variables were defined, such as population density and ports that have electrification/recharge devices.

The second segment (*Figure 3, Right*) was split into the demarcation of national marine spatial plan (*POEM - Ordenación del Espacio Marítimo, 2023*). This includes: The South Atlantic marine demarcation (SUD) with a surface of 13929 km² (1% of the total), the North Atlantic marine demarcation (NOR) with a surface of 315511 km² (29%), the Levantine-Balearic marine demarcation (LEBA) with a surface of 232182, km² (22%), the Marine demarcation of the Strait and Alborán (ESAL) with a surface of 27287 km² (3%) and the Canarian marine demarcation (CAN) with a surface of 485995 km² (45%).

Using these two study areas allows analyzing results according to administrative units and marine spatial planning areas.

Figure 3. Subdivisions of the study area, Left - coastal Autonomous Communities. Right - POEM demarcations.

3.3 Data collection and indicator development

The data collection for different data resources included was based on literature of diverse studies in the marine vessel transport sector, taking as example the transition that has taken place in Norway, where the first fully electric ferry started operating in 2015 and around 60 electric or hybrid ferries were operating by the end of 2021 (*Sæther & Moe, 2021*) with potential to continue transitioning to a 50% reduction of the Greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 compared to 2008 (*Sundvor et al., 2021*) or the case of Denmark, where in 2016 the company Siemens came to the conclusion that 7 out of 10 ferries of the country, as they usually do short journeys, were more profitable as electric ferries (*Siemens, 2016*) and where the first steps to a greener industry have already been done (*Anwar et al., 2020*).

Table 1 provides an overview of the 15 indicators to characterize the vessel trajectories. The indicators can be categorized as follows:

Study area indicators: As described in Section 5.2 two datasets were used: *Autonomic community and province* to classify the trips within specific coastal territories and *the POEM Demarcation* to group the trips according to the national marine spatial planning demarcations.

Technical indicators. These indicators describe characteristics of the vessel trajectory and technical features of the vessels analyzed. This includes the trips used to see the route different ships do and the total number of times they are done in a year; the year of construction of the ships to see if the engines of the ships are old or new branded, its length and width, the distance (in km) travelled by the vessels, the number of onshore recharging devices available at ports and the contribution in percentage of the ferries in terms of distance from the total distance of the trips with a shorter distance than 100 km.

Environmental indicators. These indicators describe the environmental conditions in the surrounding of the ferry trajectory, within 17 km buffer. This includes the *percentage % of the trip inside a protected zone*, the *sensitivity of marine habitats* to underwater noise and hazardous substance according to a score from 0 to 5 (highly sensitive) and the *average bathymetry*. Utilized to know what areas would have the highest priority in terms of the environment.

Social indicators. This indicator refers to social aspects in the coastal areas and includes population density to identify how much people would be affected from the electrification of a specific vessel trajectory.

Table 1. Indicators for the geospatial analysis

Indicator	Type of indicator	Description	Unit	Source/s
Autonomic community and province	Study area	Regional and provincial territorial limits	-	datos.gob.es, 2019
POEM Demarcation	Study area	Territorial demarcations that have been used to classify the different routes of the study	-	Ordenación del Espacio Marítimo, 2023
Trip	Technical	Different ferry routes that have been the focus of the study and which were used to represent trajectories	-	OpenStreetMap, 2023

Year	Technical	Year in which the different vessels were built	-	Free AIS Ship Tracker - VesselFinder, 2023
Trips/year	Technical	Estimated trips of each ferry per year	t/year	For example: Balearia (2023), Transmediterránea, (2023), Naviera Mar de Ons, (2023)
Contribution of ferry trip to total ferry trajectories < 100 km distance	Technical	Percentage calculation of the distance every trip brings compared to the total distance of all the trips up to 100 km length	%	OpenStreetMap, 2023
Length	Technical	Boat's length, used to calculate the dimensions	meters	Free AIS Ship Tracker - VesselFinder, 2023
Width	Technical	Boat's width, used to calculate the dimensions	meters	Free AIS Ship Tracker - VesselFinder, 2023
Distance	Technical	Distance of the ferry trips that has been studied	kilometres	OpenStreetMap, 2023
Total onshore power supplies at ports	Technical	Sum of the onshore power supply (OPS) of electrification present in each port of the trip	Number of charging devices	Onshore Power Supply Master Plan Spanish Ports, 2021
% of the trip inside a protected zone	Environmental	Meters inside a protected zone compared to the total meters of the whole trip	%	European Marine Observation and Data Network, 2023
Noise sensitivity of the habitats	Environmental	Sensitivity of the habitats affected by the trips to the noise, measured in an interval from 0 to 5 extracted from Eionet Portal	Index-	ETC/ICM, 2019; European Marine Observation and Data Network, 2023
Hazard sensitivity	Environmental	Sensitivity of the habitats affected by the trips to the hazards, measured in an interval from 0 to 5 extracted from Eionet Portal	Index-	(ETC/ICM, 2019; European Marine Observation and Data Network, 2023)

Average bathymetry	Environmental	Measurement of the mean bathymetry of each trip	meters	(European Marine Observation and Data Network, 2023)
Population density	Social	Total population affected by the trip, measured by the sum of the population in each province of the journey (departure and arrival)	Number of persons in coastal provinces	(Vangdata, 2017)

In addition to the indicators described above also other 7 variables are included:

Name: Name of the boats doing the different trips that could bring information of the engines and the frequency; *Power train*: If the engines were Electric/Non-electric, to see if it influenced the rest of the variables (distance, frequency, etc.); *Company*: To find out which companies had different vessels and if the electrification could be done in a larger scale; *Passengers, cars, speed (knots)*: these variables were found out in different sources and had the objective of comparing them with other parameters (length, width, distance, etc.) and see if there were a relation; *Average frequency trips/day*: Estimation of the total trips done by every ship calculated by the different companies timetables.

3.4. Review of social and ecological effects of electrification from vessels

At the current stage, limited amount of literature exists on the environmental and human well-being effects of the electrified vessels in marine or aquatic environments.

Table 2 provides an overview of the literature identifying the costs and benefits to the marine ecosystem and human wellbeing can be identified. Focusing on the underwater noise, hazard substances and air pollution pressures.

Table 2. Costs and benefits of the electrification in relation to different pressures

Pressure	Cost (C) or Benefit (B)	Reference
Underwater noise	<p>B - Electrified vessels can reduce noise levels that can be harmful for fish species.</p> <p>C - For marine mammal species, the reduction of noise can increase potential collisions with vessels</p> <p>B - Especially habitats and organism in coastal or inland water environments benefit from lower noise levels</p>	Parsons et al., 2020; Hemez et al., 2020

Hazardous substances	B - Electrified vessels do include little volume of toxic substances like gasoline/diesel. Therefore, intoxication risks or risks of accidents are reduced.	Hemez et al., 2020
Air pollution	B - Electrified vessels can reduce emission of air pollutants in coastal and inland water cities	Gillingham and Huang, 2020; Hemez et al., 2020
	B - There is potential benefit to public health, by reducing mortality from air pollution	Meng and Comer, 2023

In Meng and Comer, 2023 it was estimated that a full electrification scenario of the oceangoing vessels (OGVs), harbor craft, and drayage trucks would reduce a 75% and 69% in New York and New Jersey the total emissions of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and that this exposure avoided approximately 16 premature deaths per year. This was translated to public health benefit, and it was set a supposed savings from at least \$150 million every year, which “would be equal to around 10% of the annual budget of the New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene (New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene, n.d.)”. As it can be seen in figure 4, the maximum annual average PM_{2.5} would be of 0.82 µg/m³. It’s also said that the total area affected by emissions from the Port of NY/NJ would be reduced from 2,172.3 km² to 504.5 km² (Meng and Comer, 2023), showing, not only the importance of the electrification in the nucleus of the maritime transport itself, but in the near surrounding too.

Figure 4. Benefit of reduced annual average PM_{2.5} concentration (µg/m³) and monetized public health benefits (thousands \$) in New York/New Jersey in a full electrification scenario of the oceangoing vessels (OGVs), harbor craft, and drayage trucks (Meng and Comer, 2023).

In Parsons et al., 2020, through a mode deployed to the north and northeast of the Heirisson Island, it was determined that, at 55-m range, the conventionally powered ferry type produced 156 and 157 dB re 1 $\mu\text{Pa}^2 \text{m}^2$ MSL (Sound pressure level at a distance of 1 m from a hypothetical source without considering the effects of the surrounding environment) and RNL - Radiated Source Levels (taking into account the effects of the propagation medium and the environment), respectively, while the same metrics for the electric ferry were 12 dB lower. At frequencies below 500 Hz, spectral levels of the electric ferry at a range of <5 m were 10–25 dB lower than those of the conventional ferry (Table 3). The research study concludes that electric motors emit significantly less noise than those that use conventional fuels.

Table 3. Percentiles of the monopole source level and radiated noise level for each ferry type and site; EH (East Heirisson), NH (North Heirisson), MSL (Monopole Source Levels), RNL (Radiated Source Levels), (Parsons et al., 2020). Note: BW is a measurement of the signal strength on hertz (Hz)

		(dB re 1 $\mu\text{Pa}^2 \text{m}^2$)	25%	50%	75%	BW (Hz)
Conventional ferry	MSL-EH	148	156	165	125–16 000	
	RNL-EH	150	157	164	125–26 000	
	RNL-NH	148	154	159	10–26 000	
Electric ferry	MSL-EH	141	144	148	400–16 000	
	RNL-EH	140	145	151	400–26 000	
	RNL-NH	138	146	153	10–26 000	

Figure 5. Impact scores for gasoline-powered and electric pump-out boats (Hemez et al., 2020)

In *Hemez et al., 2020 (Figure 5)*, eight environmental and health impact categories were modelled, between them, the acidification, the ecotoxicity and the eutrophication, which are derivatives from hazardous substances. The research concludes that, regardless of electricity source, all electric pump-out boat (boats that provide a service of emptying the waste tank of other ships) configurations modelled had lower total impacts than a comparable gasoline-powered vessel.

3.3.1. Stakeholder engagement

The data collection performed highlighted a set of data gaps for some of the variables. For this reason, a survey was elaborated and sent to 25 different companies, trying to cover 29 of the 102 studied trips. Information was retrieved from companies' website and portals. The responses were given by 11 companies, but only 7 of them provided the information asked, covering 8 of the 29 trips without the needed data. The questions done in that surveys are collected here:

- *Is there more than one boat doing this trip?*
- *What is the number of boats operating?*
- *In what year were they built?*
- *What kind of fuel do they use (Diesel/Gas/Gasoline/Electric)?*
- *What is the maximum number of passengers they can carry?*
- *Can they carry vehicles? How many?*
- *What speed can they reach?*
- *Which are the dimensions of the boats (length and width)?*

3.4 Policy frameworks

Table 4 provides an overview of the policy strategies on European and national scale, relevant to understand targets for electrification in the transport sector. The Paris Agreement was ratified by the European Union in October 2016, and the aim of that is that the EU achieves an economy climatically neutral by 2050 (*Consejo de la Unión Europea, 2020*). The specific objectives on the study matter are collected in Zero 2050 and are: 70% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) compared to 1990, reduction of 61 % on maritime emissions from 2005 by 2030. The way to get it is based on tax marine fuels on intra-European trips, creation of a network of renewable recharging and refueling infrastructures, limitation of greenhouse emission on the ports by the boats and consideration of the real carbon footprint of the fuels, considering the entire life cycle (*zero2050.es, 2023*). This ambitious goal is planned to be executed in a long term. That's why policies planned to be executed in a less

period of time were needed, and it was elaborated COM (2016), a European policy that had objectives with a view to 2030: 40% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) compared to 1990, a 32% of renewable energy in the total gross final energy consumption, **14% of which is planned to be applied in the transport sector** and, finally, a 32.5% of improvement in energy efficiency from 2020 (*PLAN NACIONAL INTEGRADO DE ENERGÍA Y CLIMA 2021-2030, 2020*). It also was demanded by the European Union an elaboration of what is called PNIEC, and it's a national plan for every member state of the EU with a view to 2030 too, to collaborate in the European objectives. In the case of Spain, its PNIEC looks for a 23% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) compared to 1990, a 42% of renewable energy in the total gross final energy consumption, **28% of which is related to the transport** and, finally, a 39.5% improvement in energy efficiency from 2020. These were supposed to be the policy frameworks, but, in 2021, came out a set of proposals to revise and update of the EU legislation named Fit For 55 Package: 55% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) compared to 1990, increase the current EU-level target to 40% of renewable energy in the total gross final energy consumption. For that last objective, it could be achieved either a 13% greenhouse gas intensity reduction in transport or a **29 % renewable energy within the final consumption of energy in the transport sector**. A remarkable subdivision of that point is a plan to reduce the greenhouse gas intensity of the energy used on-board by ships up to 75% by 2050. Finally, a 36 % reduction at EU level for final energy consumption (Council of the European Union, 2021). This set of proposals, after a discussion of the council, were approved in June 2022, and they are the current policy framework.

Based on the review of policy directives the assumed target of ferry vessel electrification set on this study is at 28%, which it's exactly the percentage of renewable energy in the total final energy consumption for transport in the PNIEC, and it's close to the percentage of the actual European policy Fit For 55 Package.

Table 4. European and national adaptation of electrification targets

Name of the policy	Policy scale (National/ international)	Reference
Zero 2050	European	zero2050.es, 2023
COM (2016)	European	<i>PLAN NACIONAL INTEGRADO DE ENERGÍA Y CLIMA 2021-2030, 2020</i>
PNIEC	National	<i>PLAN NACIONAL INTEGRADO DE ENERGÍA Y CLIMA 2021-2030, 2020</i>
Fit for 55 Package	European	Council of the European Union, 2021

3.5. Ecological and social prioritization

The indicator database (Table 5) includes ecological and social variables that were used to create an Index of socio-ecological prioritization (SEIx). The objective of the SEIx is to define which sea areas would be most benefited from the electrification of vessels, taking into account the social and ecological conditions of the trajectories:

The SEIx is defined as follows:

$$SEIx = I_{prot} + I_{sens} + I_{pop} + I_{sw} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

In order to make indicators comparable it has been applied a normalization to the indicators extracted from *European Marine Observation and Data Network (2023)*; *ETC/ICM Report 4/2019*; *Multiple pressures and their combined effects in Europe's seas, 2020* and *Vangdata, 2017*: I_{prot} , I_{sens} , and I_{pop} were normalized as $n = n/n_{max}$, while I_{sw} had been standardized using an inverse normalization: $n = 1 - n/n_{max}$.

Table 5. Indicators for the socio-ecological index

Indicator	Description
I_{prot}	% of vessel trajectory inside a marine protected area.
I_{sens}	Average sensitivity to noise and hazardous substances of the habitats overlaying the vessel trajectory (score between 0-5).
I_{pop}	Number of populations of provinces of the coastal areas
I_{sw}	Shallow waters are referring to the water depth of the trajectories of the vessel. It is considered that in shallow waters, electrified vessel with reduced noise can have less impact to the environment. According to <i>Nikolkina and Didenkulova (2011)</i> , the shallow waters are those with less than 50 meters deep.

3.6 Analysis of electrification potentials

The analysis of the database included the following outputs that are presented in the results section and described in the following paragraphs:

Overall analysis presented in *Figure 6* show all the national ferry trajectories provided in the analysis, representing the demarcations where they are located and their respective frequencies and distances. In *Figure 7* a graphical **comparison of distances (in km) and frequency (trips/year)**, showing the relation between these two parameters, where almost all the trajectories presented in the analysis had shown an inverse relation. The frequency decreases as the distance increases (*Figure 8*). 5 different **geographic areas** were analyzed for the ferry trajectories within: Galicia, Canary Islands, Balearic Islands, Andalusia, and Valencia in relation to the different parameters, this is presented in *Table 6*. **Analysis of policy targets** were based on national and international policy frameworks analyzed. A 28% of renewable energy application in the field of transport towards 2030 for the EU and Spain was defined. *Figure 10* defines the 28% of national ferry trajectories, in terms of distance coverage, that could be electrified. Finally, the **analysis of socio-ecological aspects** was assessed, creating an order of prioritization for the trajectories where social and environmental benefits would be highest according to the Socio-Ecological Index developed in section 5.4. and mapped in *Figure 11*.

4. Results

4.1. Overall analysis

Overall results of the study are presented in *Figure 6*. The Figure shows the distances travelled by each ferry trajectory in relation to the trips/year performed. A total of 62 trips, and 102 ferry vessels, were studied. In total, the sum of the lengths for all the journeys has given a value of 6025.87 km. The actual technology feasibility for electrification of the vessels (trips up to a distance of 100 km) has been reached by 80 ferries and by 47 of the trips, showing that the highest frequency and distance travelled by ferries are located in the LEBA and ESAL demarcations. These two areas have journeys with short distances and high frequency like the case of Ibiza-Formentera (Balearic Islands) or the case of Cádiz-El Puerto de Santa María (Andalusia) in addition to longer trips but less frequented, like the case of Barcelona-Ibiza or Almería-Ghazaouet. In general terms, as *Figure 7, left* shows, given a cumulative distance (kilometers of each area compared to the total distance of all trips inside the 100 km electrification feasibility range for vessels), LEBA and CAN cover 37% and 34% of the total distance respectively. The CAN demarcation has a lot of trips really close to the 100 km distance, almost reaching the already mentioned technology limit of the feasibility for electrification of the vessels. Focusing on the Autonomic Communities (*Figure 7*), on the other hand, LEBA is formed by the Balearic Islands, but also by Valencia and Catalonia, so the results of this demarcation are distributed, getting to make the values of distance of the

Balearic Islands being surpassed by the ones of the Canary Islands, where the percentage does not vary with respect to CAN.

Figure 6. Overview of geospatial results, represented with a bubble map, showing the distance of the trips with different bubble sizes and the total trips/year representing the bubbles with a gradient of colour from blue to red. Blue lines indicate trips below 100 km distance that has been set as the limit of the technology feasibility for electrification of the vessels, while the red ones are trajectories outside this range.

Figure 7. Left - Percentage of the distance travelled within each POEM demarcation, compared to the total distance of all the trips inside the feasibility of electrification (trips below 100 km). Right - Percentage of the distance travelled within each coastal autonomous community, compared to the total distance of all the trips inside the feasibility of electrification (trips below 100 km).

Figure 8. Plot that represents the relation between the annual frequency of all the studied trips (trips/year) and the distance (in km) of themselves. The red line pulls apart the journeys that are inside the range of feasibility of electrification from those that are outside (less and more than 100 km distance).

Figure 8 plots the relation between the trip distances and their frequency. It can be seen that, in general terms, the frequency decreases as the distance increases. The more frequent trips of all the regions have been pointed out, showing that except from Tenerife-La Gomera, and Ibiza-Formentera, where the vessels can carry out vehicles (Ro-Ro ships), all the other journeys are exclusively operated by passenger boats: Santoña-Laredo for Cantabria, Mundaka-Ibarrangelu (Laida) for the Basque Country, Vigo-Moaña for Galicia, Cádiz-El Puerto de Santa María for Andalusia and Santa Pola-Tabarca for Valencia; Ro-Ro ships: Tenerife-La Gomera for the Canary Islands and Ibiza-Formentera for the Balearic Islands. The main difference between these last two trips and the rest is that they are interisland, while the others are local journeys. The values of frequency of different ships doing the same trip has been summed to have a representative value that could be observed on the plot.

Based on the presented overall results in *Figure 3*, the study area was divided into geographic areas based on the Balearic Islands, Canary Islands and coastal regions of Andalusia, Galicia and Valencia (*Table 6*), where the distance difference of the trips can be seen. Not the case of the Basque Country and Cantabria, which have trips with frequencies up to 14,600 for Mundaka-Ibarrangu (Laida) or 11,040 for Santoña-Laredo, but they all are short distance journeys. If the POEM demarcation of the main trips of each region are analyzed, it can be observed that Vigo-Moaña is on NOR and have frequency values of almost 9,776, with a distance of 4.38 km (*Table 6.a*), the trips of Canary Islands are on CAN, and, even tho they have lower frequencies than other regions, for example Tenerife-La Gomera, is done 5,110 times per year, but with a length of 41.34 km (*Table 6.b*). The opposite case is on the tours of Andalusia, where the frequencies are high, but the distances are short, being clearly pictured

on two of them, both on SUD demarcation, Ayamonte-Villa Real de Santo Antonio, has a frequency of 8,760 trips/year and only 2.04 km of distance and Cádiz-El Puerto de Santa María has a frequency of 13,662 and a length of 9.05 km (*Table 6.c*). In Valencia, the frequencies and the distances are not as high or long as other regions, but they have been pointed because they contribute to the navigation of the LEBA demarcation. Santa Pola-Tabarca possesses a frequency of 5,840 and a length of 8.74 km (*Table 6.e*). Finally, The Balearic Islands have the most frequented trip of all the regions, Ibiza-Formentera has 7 ships operating simultaneously with a total frequency of 18250 trips/year and a distance of 21.03 km. They also have long distance trips that are part of the LEBA demarcation too.

Table 6. Relation between distance of the trips and the frequency by the most important coastal regions: a. Galicia, b. Canary Islands, c. Balearic Islands, d. Andalusia, e. Valencia. The red line on the different plots pulls apart the journeys that are inside the feasibility of electrification from those that are outside (less or more than 100 km length).

c)

d)

e)

Figure 9. Geospatial representation of the ports, which already have onshore power supplies by a bubble map, that shows the number of devices with different bubble sizes. The red trips are the ones that are outside the actual technological feasibility range for the electrification of the vessels, and the blue ones are the ones that are inside it. Source: (Onshore Power Supply Master Plan Spanish Ports, 2021)

In general terms, LEBA, with 13 recharging devices is the demarcation that possess more electrified devices, followed by CAN and ESAL, having 7 each one (*Table 7*), but, if the Autonomous Community table is analyzed (*Table 8*) Andalusia has the most onshore power supplies, with 13, while Balearic Islands has only 3. This is because, as it is already mentioned, Andalusia includes two demarcations; ESAL and SUD, and LEBA is formed by Valencia, Catalonia, and the Balearic Islands. It's important to stand out that many of the trips done in this first two Coastal Autonomous Communities inside LEBA have a lot of trips that are bound for the Balearic Islands, so their devices could be used if the distances were shorter than 100 km. If the ports are analyzed more specifically, the ones with more onshore power supplies are: The port of Huelva (Andalusia), with 4 devices, the port of Algeciras (Andalusia), and the port of Bilbao (Basque Country), both with 3 devices.

Table 7. Number of recharging devices in ports for different vessel types in relation to the different POEM demarcations. Note: Ro-Ro: Ships that can carry out vehicle transportation. Source: Onshore Power Supply Master Plan Spanish Ports, 2021.

Demarcation	Ro-Ro	Containers	Cruisers	Others	Total
LEBA	6	4	1	2	13
CAN	4	0	0	3	7
ESAL	5	2	0	0	7
SUD	2	1	1	2	6
NOR	2	1	1	0	4

Table 8. Number of recharging devices in ports for different vessel types in relation to the different Autonomic Communities. Note: Ro-Ro: Ships that can carry out vehicle transportation. Source: Onshore Power Supply Master Plan Spanish Ports, 2021.

Autonomic communities	Ro-Ro	Containers	Cruisers	Others	Total
Andalusia	5	3	1	2	11
Valencia	2	3	1	2	8
Canary Islands	4	0	0	3	7
Basque Country	2	1	1	0	4
Balearic Islands	3	0	0	0	3
Catalonia	1	1	0	0	2
Melilla	2	0	0	0	2

If the 28% of renewable energies in the transport sector defined in section 5.4 is considered, there has to be a prioritization of electrification. As it has already been said, the most suitable trajectories to be electrified are the ones with less distance to cover from the departure to the arrival (Yang et al., 2022). For this reason, the percentage of contribution to the total distance of all the trips up to 100 km has been calculated and mapped (Figure 10). The results show that 27.89 % of the total distance of the journeys is covered by the first 36 trips, being operated by 49 ships. The last trip inside this percentage is Ibiza-Formentera (Balearic Islands), having a length of 21,03 km. As mentioned in Section 5.1 (Figure 2) this ferry trajectory will be electrified in summer 2023. According to the map below other ferry trajectories that have the potential to be electrified include Vigo-Moaña (Galicia), Cádiz-El Puerto de Santa María (Andalusia), Santa Pola-Tabarca (Valencia), Santiago de la Ribera-La Manga del Mar Menor

(Murcia), Port de Sóller-Sa Calobra (Balearic Islands), Pollença-Cala del Pi de la Posada (Balearic Islands) or Catamarán Valencia (Valencia), and Calpe-Altea (Valencia).

Figure 10. Trajectories with potential fulfillment of national and European policy targets.

Figure 11 provides a case study for the calculation of the Socio-Ecological Index for the LEBA demarcation. This is selected because it shows highest scores of socio-ecological prioritizations. Ferry trajectories with higher SEI_x should be prioritized for electric conversion, because of the reduction of possible social and marine environmental effects. In terms of priority, there were nine trips that exceeded a value of 2.7 in the socio-ecological index. This includes for example: Catamarán Calpe-Altea (2.91), Santiago de la Ribera-La Manga del Mar Menor (2.89), Port de Sóller-Sa Calobra (2.84), Santa Pola-Tabarca (2.84), Ciudadela-Alcúdia (2.83), Pollença-Cala del Pi de la Posada (2.74), Ibiza-Formentera (2.74) and Catamarán Valencia (2.72). All the ferry trajectories are inside or partially inside protected areas (82 to 98% of the trajectory). The summed sensitivity of noise and hazardous substances of the marine habitats ranges from 2.98 to 3.5 score.

Figure 11. Trajectories worth prioritizing according to socio-ecological impacts. The map also includes information on the distribution of protected areas.

5. Discussion

The study presents an overview of the vessel electrification potentials on the Spanish territory, aiming to establish a general order of prioritization and classifying it into the different areas of the country. It was found that, in fact, the Balearic Islands, one of the zones that should be given more priority, is precisely an area where the first electrification efforts have already been applied. A clear example of that, is the trip Ibiza-Formentera, which already has the first electric boats operating and has forecasts to continue improving in this regard. On the other hand, Valencia, what could be considered as a high prioritization area, mainly because of the socio-ecological aspects, seems to already possess several electrical devices and the area of Andalusia has a similar profile but with more incidence in the frequency of journeys than in the socio-ecological aspects.

The methodological steps presented in this study are based on a literature review on most recent methods for geospatial analysis of electrification potentials (*Sundvor et al., 2021*). The database developed in this study provides a novel indicator database for the future analysis

of other type of vessels, for instance cargo ships or tankers. This data is available on the EMODNet Geoviewer. In addition, the presented indicator datasets also provide other information that needs to be included, to understand the actual electrification potential in the different study areas, namely the type of motor, full passenger information (in terms of number of passengers), average number of trips per year and the Deadweight tonnage or tons deadweight (DWT), which is a measure of how much weight a ship can carry.

This is information not yet available in the data collection process and would need to be calculated if requested by the different ferry providers. The data collection and configuration were challenging by the lack of online resources for small scale urban passenger trips.

Also, important datasets related battery discharge and weights are not presented and often based on assumptions that will need to be taken into consideration in the future (e.g., *Sundvor et al., 2021*).

The study makes a review of existing knowledge on the environmental effects of electrified vessels on different ecological components (for example *Hemez et al., 2021; Meng, Z., & Comer, 2023; Nunes et al., 2020; Parsons et al., 2020*). The literature showed that there is only a little segment of studies, mostly in Australia, related to measuring the impacts to fish species, marine mammals and habitats. This study contributed to this literature by proposing a simple index based on geospatial data that can be used to understand which trajectories of vessels would benefit the most in from an electrification.

Our results show that local transport in coastal areas and inland water would benefit the most and would make a conversion more feasible given the shorter trajectories to be made, given their presence in protected areas and given their location in highly populated urban areas.

During the interviews, it was noticed that some of the operators of smaller vessels had explored electrification options, but, as they said, any of them seemed to fit their needs because they operated only with one boat, and they could not fully load their ship in their day to day. The problem of one of the companies, for example, was that the boat did a trip influenced by the tides, and, when they were low, it sailed with a depth up to 0.5 m. This required the use of an outboard motor, and with this kind of engine, I quote verbatim “*There is currently no autonomy that gives me reliability to work fully in the summer season*”. That exemplifies the fact that these types of technologies are still in an early stage of development, and that this sector still has a lot of potential for improvement.

It also was observed that, in some responses of the interviews, there were many more boats than appeared on the company’s websites operating on the same trip, which emphasizes the challenges of information resources required for the research.

The presented database and maps are important for decision-making at local/municipal, regional, and national level for decision makers. This is because the analysis focuses on ferry for local and urban transport, and municipalities can use it to better understand conversion needs. Regional authorities can direct funding mechanisms to support small scale ferry operators in the conversion. On national level study is framed into 5 sub-territories (Galicia, Balearic, Canary Island, Gibraltar-Andalusia, Valencia) and is also subdivided into the 5 demarcations of the POEM. Dividing the study into the POEM provides knowledge to understand how demarcations perform in terms of potential reduction of emissions and in terms of potential reduction of effects on the marine environment.

6. Conclusions

The decarbonization process is already underway both at the European and Spanish levels. Although it is in what could be considered the early stages of development, there are projections that advancements in this field will continue to increase over the years, progressing towards what is known as an ecologically neutral economy. In this process, the transportation sector plays a crucial role, so it is expected that many of the efforts will be directed towards this sector. It is the responsibility of each member state of the European Union to contribute to this process, optimizing the resources employed to achieve it.

In terms of transportation, many countries have already made significant progress. Specifically, if we look at the maritime transport sector, we can observe examples such as Norway or Denmark, which clearly lead the decarbonization process and can serve as a source of inspiration for countries that are still in earlier stages of this process, such as Spain.

The Spanish territory has a wide variety of regular maritime routes, so it is not surprising that this sector significantly contributes to greenhouse gas emissions. Initial efforts to reduce these emissions have already been made, but there is still a long way to go, and future efforts need to be focused. For example, this project provides identification of the information gaps related to the replacement of the ferry boats and technical challenges that can be only addressed using surveys and interviews.

Regarding the electrification of ships, both to avoid battery depletion during trips and to reduce focused pollution, thus minimizing environmental and social impact, the best option at the current stage is to implement it in small ports and for journeys that do not involve very long distances. In Spain, there are several routes that fit this profile, so other characteristics such

as the type of ship engines, passenger capacity, or deadweight tonnage need to be considered.

There have been difficulties in collecting data and finding certain information, which has resulted in reduced reliability regarding the observation of results. This should be improved to facilitate its use in future studies, even so, the developed database could be further developed through collaborations with different experts in the fields of environmental, protection, planning, naval engineering, etc.

7. Bibliography

1. Anwar, S., Zia, M., Rashid, M., De Rubens, G. Z., & Enevoldsen, P. (2020). Towards Ferry Electrification in the Maritime Sector. *Energies*, 13(24), 6506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13246506>
2. Baleària. (2023) Flota y acomodación - Baleària. Baleària. <https://www.balearia.com/es/flota>
3. Baleària (2023) New electric ferry - Cap de Barbaria - Baleària. <https://www.balearia.com/en/cap-de-barbaria-ferry-electric>
4. Consejo de la Unión Europea. (2020). Acuerdo de París sobre el Cambio Climático. Consejo Europeo. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/es/policias/climate-change/paris-agreement/>
5. Council of the European Union. (2021). Fit for 55. European Council. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policias/green-deal/fit-for-55-the-eu-plan-for-a-green-transition/#what>
6. Danish Electric Ferry Completes World-record 90km Voyage on a Single Charge. (2022, June 20). MarineLink. <https://www.marinelink.com/news/danish-electric-ferry-completes-497466>
7. datos.gob.es. (2019, January 31). Base de Datos de Divisiones Administrativas de España - Conjunto de datos. <https://datos.gob.es/es/catalogo/e00125901-spaingllm>
8. Electrification: the path to green ports. (2023, February 2). Endesa. <https://www.endesa.com/en/the-e-face/ecological-transition/ports-verds-electrification-spain>
9. EU (2023). SDG 5 - Gender equality: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. En Eurostat. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=SDG_5_-_Gender_equality#Gender_equality_in_the_EU:_overview_and_key_trends
10. European Marine Observation and Data Network. (2023). EMODnet Map Viewer. European Commission. <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/>
11. ETC/ICM Report 4/2019: Multiple pressures and their combined effects in Europe's seas. (2020, January 27). Eionet Portal. <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-icm/products/etc-icm-reports/etc-icm-report-4-2019-multiple-pressure-and-their-combined-effects-in-europes-seas>
12. Free AIS Ship Tracker - VesselFinder. (2023). <https://www.vesselfinder.com/>

13. Gillingham, K.T., Huang, P., 2020. Long-Run Environmental and Economic Impacts of Electrifying Waterborne Shipping in the United States. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54, 9824–9833. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c032986>
14. Hemez, C., Chiu, J., Ryan, E.C., Sun, J., Dubrow, R., Pascucilla, M., 2020. Environmental and health impacts of electric service vessels in the recreational boating industry. *Water Practice and Technology* 15, 781–796. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2020.063>
15. Kersey, J., Popovich, N., & Phadke, A. (2022). Rapid battery cost declines accelerate the prospects of all-electric interregional container shipping. *Nature Energy*, 7(7), 664-674. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-022-01065-y>
16. La Información (2023, 22 enero). La transición energética de los puertos españoles requiere de 4.500 millones. *La Información*. <https://www.lainformacion.com/economia-negocios-y-finanzas/transicion-energetica-puertos-requiere-4500-millones/2880137/>
17. Meng, Z., & Comer, B. (2023). Electrifying ports to reduce diesel pollution from ships and trucks and benefit public health: Case studies of the Port of Seattle and the Port of New York and New Jersey.
18. Monitor Deloitte. (2020). Los Territorios No Peninsulares 100% descarbonizados en 2040: la vanguardia de la transición energética en España. <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/es/Documents/estrategia/Deloitte-ES-estrategia-descarbonizacion-territorios-no-peninsulares.pdf>
19. Naviera Mar de Ons. (2023, 18 mayo). Naviera Mar de Ons: viajes a Cíes, Ons y mucho más. <https://www.mardeons.es/>
20. Nikolkina, Irina & Didenkulova (2011). Rogue waves in 2006-2010. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/The-definition-of-the-shallow-deep-and-coastal-rogue-waves_fig8_258540027.
21. Npanmontojo. (2020). Los ricos son los principales contribuyentes al cambio climático. *EL ÁGORA DIARIO*. <https://www.elagoradiario.com/desarrollo-sostenible/cambio-climatico/ricos-cambio-climatico-pobres/#:~:text=El%20transporte%20es%20una%20de,energ%C3%ADa%20de%20combustible%20para%20veh%C3%ADculos>
22. Nunes, R.A.O., Alvim-Ferraz, M.C.M., Martins, F.G., Calderay-Cayetano, F., Durán-Grados, V., Moreno-Gutiérrez, J., Jalkanen, J.-P., Hannuniemi, H., Sousa, S.I.V., 2020. Shipping emissions in the Iberian Peninsula and the impacts on air quality. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 20, 9473–9489. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-9473-2020>
23. OECD. (2021). Gender and the Environment: Building Evidence and Policies to Achieve the SDGs. <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/3d32ca39-en/index.html?itemId=/content/publication/3d32ca39-en>
24. OpenStreetMap. (2023). OpenStreetMap. <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>
25. Ops Master Plan Spanish Ports. (2021, April 29). Power@berth - Ops Spanish Ports. Power@berth. <https://poweratberth.eu/?lang=en>
26. Ordenación del Espacio Marítimo. (2023). <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cartografia-y-sig/ide/descargas/costas-medio-marino/poem.aspx>
27. Parsons, M.J.G., Duncan, A.J., Parsons, S.K., Erbe, C., 2020. Reducing vessel noise: An example of a solar-electric passenger ferry. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 147, 3575–3583. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0001264>
28. Parsons, M.J.G., Erbe, C., Meekan, M.G., Parsons, S.K., 2021. A Review and Meta-Analysis of Underwater Noise Radiated by Small (<25 m Length) Vessels.

29. Journal of Marine Science and Engineering (2021) 9, 827.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9080827>
30. Perčić, M., Vladimir, N., Fan, A., 2021. Techno-economic assessment of alternative marine fuels for inland shipping in Croatia. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 148, 111363.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111363>
31. PLAN NACIONAL INTEGRADO DE ENERGÍA Y CLIMA 2021-2030. (2020, January 20). https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/ministerio/planes-estrategias/plan-nacional-integrado-energia-clima/plannacionalintegradodeenergiayclima2021-2030_tcm30-546623.pdf
32. Sæther, S.R., Moe, E., 2021. A green maritime shift: Lessons from the electrification of ferries in Norway. Energy Research & Social Science 81, 102282.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102282>
33. Siemens. (2016). Electrification of Denmark's ferry fleet : Study: 7 out of 10 ferries are more profitable after conversion to electrical propulsion. En [siemens.dk/eferry](https://assets.new.siemens.com/siemens/assets/api/uuid:01a7cbed-c7fc-4884-a591-bc5c5fed2f0e/study-electrification-e.pdf).
<https://assets.new.siemens.com/siemens/assets/api/uuid:01a7cbed-c7fc-4884-a591-bc5c5fed2f0e/study-electrification-e.pdf>
34. Sundvor, I., Thorne, R.J., Danebergs, J., Aarskog, F., Weber, C., 2021. Estimating the replacement potential of Norwegian high-speed passenger vessels with zero-emission solutions. Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment 99, 103019.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2021.103019>
35. Tidey, A. (2019, August 21). World's largest all-electric ferry sets sail in Denmark. euronews. <https://www.euronews.com/my-europe/2019/08/20/world-s-largest-all-electric-ferry-sets-sail-in-denmark>
36. Transmediterránea. (2023). Nuestra flota. Armas.
<https://www.trasmediterranea.es/es/flota>
37. UN (2023, 10 February). The Lack of Gender Equality in Science Is Everyone's Problem | United Nations. <https://www.un.org/en/un-chronicle/lack-gender-equality-science-everyone%E2%80%99s-problem>
38. Vangdata. (2017). shapefiles provincias espana. CARTO.
https://vangdata.carto.com/tables/shapefiles_provincias_espana/public/map
39. Yang, S., Yuan, J., Nian, V., Li, L., Li, H., 2022. Economics of marinised offshore charging stations for electrifying the maritime sector. Applied Energy 322, 119389.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.119389>
40. zero2050.es. (2023, 23 February). European regulation - zero 2050. cero 2050.
<https://cero2050.es/en/eu-regulation/>